

Synthesis of nickel(II) complexes with some thiocarbamide derivatives

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1,2-Diisothiocabamido ethane was found to act as a potential tetradenate (NSSN) chelating agent. Several different chelating reagents of this type were synthesised and through their interaction with Ni^{II} salts, different Ni^{II} complexes e.g. [Ni(NSSN)(NO₃)] were prepared. These complexes were characterized by their elemental analysis, magnetic behaviour, electrical conductance and IR spectra. Antibacterial activities of the complexes have been determined and most of them are found highly active.

In our previous communication, we reported the synthesis of some new thiocarbamide derivatives¹. These compounds having more than one donor atom have been found to act as a potential polydentate chelating ligands. We report herein the synthesis of Ni^{II} complexes (**1**, **2** and **3**) from the prepared three thiocarbamides, viz. 1,2-diisothiocabamidoethane (L¹), 1,2-diphenylisothiocabamido ethane (L²) and *S*-benzylisothioureia (L³). Anticipating the antibacterial property of complexes, antibacterial property of these compounds against various bacteria has also been tested.

Results and discussion

The analytical and molar conductance data of the complexes TEN (**1**), BPEN (**2**) and TBN (**3**) are presented in Table 1.

The molar conductivities of (**1**, **2** and **3**) complexes were measured in DMSO. The conductance values (1.5, 1.3 and 1.9 cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively) reveal that these complexes behave as non-electrolyte. Because of the attachments of ionic (-NO₃) group in the coordination sphere of these Ni complexes according to the scheme: Ni complex in DMSO → [Ni L(NO₃)₂], where L = (i) 1,2-diisothiocabamido ethane (L¹); (ii) 1,2-diphenylisothiocabamido ethane (L²) and (iii) *S*-benzylisothiocabamide (L³).

From the magnetic measurements data of Ni complexes, TEN, BPEN and TBN, they are found to be high spin complexes. They show diamagnetic character, corresponding to their no unpaired electrons (Table 1). Therefore all of these Ni complexes are of 6 folded octahedral geometrical shape.

IR spectral data of L¹ are given in Table 2. Being a po-

1

2

3

where R = H, *t*-butyl, phenyl, *p*-anisyl, *p*-tolyl

Table 1. Colour and analytical data of the complexes (1-3)*

Compd.	Complex	Colour	Yield %	Decomp. temp. °C	TLC ^a <i>R_f</i>	Metal (%)		Molar conduction cm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
						Calcd.	Found		
1	TEN	Black	95	225	0.50	16.32	16.01	1.5	Diamagnetic
2	BPEN	Yellow	63	314	0.45	11.32	12.10	1.3	Diamagnetic
3	TBN	Reddish black	68	272	0.55	11.28	12.15	1.9	Diamagnetic

*All the complexes gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

^aEluent : benzene : acetone (1 : 1, v/v) mixture.

tentially quadridentate neutral ligand, L¹ coordinates with Ni through its two nitrogen and two sulphur atoms. The ligand shows characteristic bands at 3255, 1637, 1222 and 1014 cm⁻¹. These bands may be attributed to the $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C})$, modes respectively. On the other hand all of the complexes prepared from L¹, show $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, at 1633 to 1616 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). These spectral data indicate that the Ni^{II} ions are not coordinated with imino nitrogen (C=NH).

The IR spectra also give positive evidence supporting that the Ni^{II} ions are coordinated with two nitrogen and two sulphur atoms of the ligand. This is also supported by the fact that $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ bands of the complexes, e.g. TEN, TENB, TENP etc. are found to be shifted to lower frequencies (3226 to 3150 cm⁻¹) (Table 2), as compared to the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ band observed for the corresponding free ligand (3255 cm⁻¹). The shifting values of various complexes are different. This shift in $\nu(\text{NH}/\text{NH}_2)$ band provide further evidence, supporting that a pair of amino (-NH₂) nitrogens are involved in coordination. This is also apparent from the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C})$ modes at (950–827 cm⁻¹) in the IR spectra of all complexes

prepared from L¹. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C})$ band observed at 1014 cm⁻¹ for free ligand is shifted by (54–187 cm⁻¹) in these complexes, indicating that both of the sulphur atoms are coordinated with Ni^{II} ion.

Further, IR spectra of these complexes show the existence of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ modes at (520–468 cm⁻¹) and (495–407 cm⁻¹) respectively, this is a further evidence for the coordination of nitrogen and sulphur with nickel(II) ion.

The IR spectra of complexes TENB, TENP, TENA, TENT show that the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ mode at 1166–1070 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) indicate the presence of (-CS-) group in these complexes prepared from TEN.

Similarly, the IR spectral data of L², L³ and their derivatives are shown in Table 2.

Antibacterial activities of all the complexes were determined by paper-disc method² against different strains of Gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptococcus B-haemolyticus*, *S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Sulmonella typhi*, *E.G.L*, *B. megantherium*, *Shigella dysentiae* and *S. Boydii*) bacteria respectively. The complexes were found to be highly active (zone of inhibition 15–22 mm) in

Table 2. IR spectral data for the ligand L¹, L², L³ and their derivatives (band maxima cm⁻¹)

Compd.	$\nu(\text{NH}_2/\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$
L ¹	3255	1637	1222	–	1014	–	–
TEN	3226	1633	1263	–	827	486	416
TENB	3215	1612	1336	1166	930	510	450
TENP	3215	1622	1344	1070	933	486	420
TENA	3150	1616	1311	1141	950	520	495
TENT	323	1616	1186	1139	950	475	407
L ²	3440	1575	1280	–	900	–	–
BPEN	3328	1560	1255	–	758	520	498
BPTT	3149	1554	1286	1141	812	530	487
L ³	3332	1637	1452	–	1070	–	–
TBNB	3024	1492	1452	–	1060	556	460
TBNP	3220	1510	467	1243	1033	582	522

comparison to free ligands, L¹, L² and L³. A survey of the available literature on similar compounds shows that they possess inhibitory action against different pathogenic bacteria^{3,4}. The present result is satisfactory and compares our compounds with the antibacterial activities of other thiocarbamides already reported in the literature.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were doubled-distilled before use. M.ps. were determined using a Gallenkamp AZ 6512 apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Pye-Unicam SP3-200 spectrophotometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel GF₂₅₄ plates and spots were visualized by exposure to iodine vapour.

The ligands, 1,2-diisothiocarbamido ethane (L¹), 1,2-diphenylisothiocarbamido ethane (L²) and *S*-benzylisothiocarbamide (L³) were prepared according to reported methods¹. The alkyl and arylisothiocyanates were prepared following the usual methods⁵. The complexes were analysed for metal and sulphur by standard method⁶ and nitrogen by kjeldahl method⁷. The electrical conductance values were measured at room temperature using a conductivity meter of type CG857 No. 71798 Schottgerate GmbH. For the measurement of magnetic susceptibilities, the Sherwood Scientific Magnetic Susceptibility Balance (M.S.B.) was used.

*Preparation of nickel complex of 1,2-diisothiocarbamido ethane*⁸ (TEN) : 1,2-Diisothiocarbamido ethane, L¹ (1.78 g) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml) in a 250 ml round bottom flask and acetone solution of nickel nitrate (1.82 g) was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 30 min. A black colour was appeared. This solution was cooled and 50 ml of distilled water was added. A black solid product was obtained. The residue was filtered, washed with water and finally with acetone and dried in a desiccator (yield 2.70 g, m.p. 225°C). Similarly, the other complexes (BPEN and TBN) were prepared from 1,2-diphenylisothiocarbamido ethane and *S*-benzylisothiocarbamide.

*Reaction of nickel complex of ligand L¹ (TEN) with *t*-butylisothiocyanate :*

Formation of the related thiocarbamide : Nickel complex of the ligand L¹ (0.35 g) was dissolved in DMSO (10 ml) in a 100 ml round bottom flask and *t*-

butylisothiocyanate (2 ml) was added to it. The mixture was shaken gently and refluxed for 1 h at about 110°C. The mixture was cooled and to it distilled water (15 ml) was added. It was then allowed to stand for some time. The mixture was filtered and the white product obtained was washed with alcohol and dried in a desiccator (yield 0.24 g, m.p. 150°C).

Similarly, the reaction was also extended to other isothiocyanates to get their corresponding thiocarbamides.

*Determination of antibacterial activities of the prepared thiocarbamides*² : A solution of all the complexes were prepared in DMSO in such a manner that 10 µL contained 30 µg of the sample. Filter paper discs were taken in a petridish and test solution was applied on a disc with the help of a micro-pipette. Thus disc containing 30 µg of sample was prepared. The sample impregnated discs were placed gently on solidified agar plates seeded with the organisms with the help of sterile forceps to ensure contact with the media. The plates were then kept in a refrigerator at 4°C for 24 h so that the materials absorbed into discs could get sufficient time to diffuse into the media. Finally, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. After 24 h incubation, the antibacterial activity of the complexes were determined by measuring the zone of inhibition in term of mm by a transparent scale.

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